

Luminous flux and solid angle through
triangles and n-gons

Harald Schröer

2015

Chapter 1

General n-gons

We view the following figures:

$$\vec{p}_1, \vec{p}_2, \vec{p}_3 \neq \vec{0}$$

We search the luminous flux through the triangle. The point source Q has the luminous intensity I . The light source and the triangle are in vacuum. The point source Q is in the origin of R^3 . $\vec{p}_1, \vec{p}_2, \vec{p}_3 \in R^3$ are localized vectors of the triangle. From Q we make a central projection of this triangle to the **unit sphere**. The result is a spherical triangle. The spherical triangle has the side angles a, b, c . The task is to find the solid angle through this spherical triangle.

The angles a, b, c can be described with the scalar product:

$$\cos a = \frac{\vec{p}_2 \cdot \vec{p}_3}{|\vec{p}_2| \cdot |\vec{p}_3|} \quad \cos b = \frac{\vec{p}_1 \cdot \vec{p}_3}{|\vec{p}_1| \cdot |\vec{p}_3|} \quad \cos c = \frac{\vec{p}_1 \cdot \vec{p}_2}{|\vec{p}_1| \cdot |\vec{p}_2|} \quad (1.1)$$

The angles α, β, γ follow with the cosine law for sides:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos a &= \cos b \cos c + \sin b \sin c \cos \alpha \\ \cos b &= \cos a \cos c + \sin a \sin c \cos \beta \\ \cos c &= \cos a \cos b + \sin a \sin b \cos \gamma \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

or:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \alpha &= \frac{\cos a - \cos b \cos c}{\sin b \sin c} \\ \cos \beta &= \frac{\cos b - \cos a \cos c}{\sin a \sin c} \\ \cos \gamma &= \frac{\cos c - \cos a \cos b}{\sin a \sin b} \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

We can use the spherical law of sines, too.

$$\frac{\sin a}{\sin \alpha} = \frac{\sin b}{\sin \beta} = \frac{\sin c}{\sin \gamma} \quad (1.4)$$

Before we are able to use this law, we must determine one of the angles α, β, γ .

If ε° is the spherical excess, then it is valid (degree and radian measure):

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon^\circ &= \alpha^\circ + \beta^\circ + \gamma^\circ - 180^\circ \\ \varepsilon &= \alpha + \beta + \gamma - \pi \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

The area A of the spherical triangle on the unit sphere is:

$$A = \frac{\pi \cdot \varepsilon^\circ}{180^\circ} \quad \text{or} \quad A = \varepsilon \quad (1.6)$$

This area is equal to the solid angle Ω .

For the luminous flux Φ we have:

$$\Phi = I \cdot \varepsilon = I \cdot (\alpha + \beta + \gamma - \pi) \quad (1.7)$$

[α, β, γ in radian measure]

This is a simple way to the solid angle through the triangle. Other formulas for the solid angle can be found in Eriksson [1]. Liu [2] p.270 equation (2.2)

and Todhunter [3] Chapter VII, VIII.
 Every n-gon can be separated into triangles.

$$\Omega_{n-Eck} = \text{sum of } \Omega_{Dreiecke} \quad (1.8)$$

some examples:

a)

6-gon

b)

7-gon

c)

9-gon

We can use the method of this chapter or the equation (2.2) p.270 in Liu [2] for every triangle. Another method for n-gons is developed by Asvestas [4]. The separation to a) and b) is better than the separation in c). But not every n-gon can be separated as in a) or b).

Chapter 2

The vertical regular n-gon

In chapter 1 we become acquainted with a general method for calculating solid angles. Now we view a special case - the vertical regular n-gon.

Fig. 1

$$\alpha^\circ = \frac{360^\circ}{n}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{2\pi}{n} \quad (\text{RADIAN MEASURE})$$

The regular n-gon has the exterior circle radius R and the distance r to the light source Q . The whole room is in vacuum. The projection of this triangle to the unit sphere is the following spherical triangle:

Fig.2

γ is the projection of α and β the projection of $\frac{180^\circ - \alpha}{2}$.
Using the cosine law for sides:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos b &= \cos^2 c + \sin^2 c \cdot \cos \gamma \\ \cos c &= \cos b \cos c + \sin b \sin c \cdot \cos \beta \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

It follows:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{\cos b - \cos^2 c}{\sin^2 c} \quad (2.2)$$

$$\cos \beta = \frac{\cos c - \cos b \cos c}{\sin b \sin c} = \frac{\cos c(1 - \cos b)}{\sin b \sin c} \quad (2.3)$$

At fig. 1 we can see the following triangle:

We calculate:

$$\begin{aligned} e &= \sqrt{r^2 + R^2 \cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} \\ f &= \sqrt{r^2 + R^2} \\ \sin \frac{b}{2} &= \frac{a}{2f} = \frac{a}{2\sqrt{r^2 + R^2}} \\ \cos \frac{b}{2} &= \frac{e}{f} = \sqrt{\frac{r^2 + R^2 \cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}{r^2 + R^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

It is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} \sin 2a &= 2 \sin a \cos a \\ \cos 2a &= 1 - 2 \sin^2 a \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\sin b = 2 \sin \frac{b}{2} \cos \frac{b}{2} = \frac{a \sqrt{r^2 + R^2} \cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}{r^2 + R^2} \quad (2.6)$$

$$\cos b = 1 - 2 \sin^2 \frac{b}{2} = 1 - \frac{a^2}{2(r^2 + R^2)} \quad (2.7)$$

see fig. 1:

$$\sin c = \frac{R}{\sqrt{R^2 + r^2}} \quad \cos c = \frac{r}{\sqrt{R^2 + r^2}} \quad (2.8)$$

$$\sin^2 c = \frac{R^2}{R^2 + r^2} \quad \cos^2 c = \frac{r^2}{R^2 + r^2} \quad (2.9)$$

We insert (7) and (9) in the equation (2):

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{1 - \frac{a^2}{2(r^2 + R^2)} - \frac{r^2}{R^2 + r^2}}{\frac{R^2}{R^2 + r^2}} = \frac{2(r^2 + R^2) - a^2 - 2r^2}{2R^2} = \frac{2R^2 - a^2}{2R^2}$$

$$\cos \gamma = 1 - \frac{a^2}{2R^2} \quad (2.10)$$

Then we insert (7) and (8) in equation (3):

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \beta &= \frac{\frac{r}{\sqrt{R^2 + r^2}} \cdot \left(1 - 1 + \frac{a^2}{2(r^2 + R^2)}\right)}{\frac{R}{\sqrt{R^2 + r^2}} \cdot \frac{a \sqrt{r^2 + R^2} \cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}{r^2 + R^2}} \\ \cos \beta &= \frac{ra}{2R} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2} \cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

The spherical excess ε of this triangle can be written:

$$\varepsilon = 2\beta + \gamma - \pi \quad (\text{in radian measure}) \quad (2.12)$$

For the solid angle Ω through the whole n-gon we have:

$$\Omega = \varepsilon \cdot n \quad (2.13)$$

We conclude for the luminous flux (the light source has the constant luminous intensity I):

$$\Phi = I \cdot \Omega = I \cdot \varepsilon \cdot n = I \cdot n \cdot (2\beta + \gamma - \pi) \quad (2.14)$$

At fig. 1 we see:

$$\sin \frac{\alpha}{2} = \frac{a}{2R} \quad (2.15)$$

with (5):

$$\cos \alpha = 1 - 2 \sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} = 1 - \frac{a^2}{2R^2} \quad (2.16)$$

with (10) follows:

$$\alpha = \gamma \quad (2.17)$$

Then we insert (11) for β in (14) and notice $\gamma = \alpha = \frac{2\pi}{n}$ (fig.1) we obtain:

$$\Phi = I \cdot n \cdot \left[2 \cdot \arccos \left(\frac{r \cdot a}{2 \cdot P \cdot \sqrt{r^2 + R^2 \cos^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{n} \right)}} \right) + \pi \cdot \left(\frac{2}{n} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (2.18)$$

$$r > 0$$

From (15) we get:

$$\sin \left(\frac{\pi}{n} \right) = \frac{a}{2R} \quad (2.19)$$

(18) and (19) are valid in radian measure.

Bibliography

- [1] Folke Eriksson "On the Measure of Solid Angles" Mathematics Magazine Vol.63 No.3 June 1990 p.184-187
- [2] A. Liu, B. Joe "Relationship between Tetrahedron shape measures" BIT 34 (1994) p.268-287
- [3] I. Todhunter, J.G. Leathem "Spherical Trigonometry" Macmillan London 1901
- [4] John Asvestas, David Englund "Computing the solid angle subtended by a planar figure" Optical Engineering December 1994 Vol.33 No.12 p.4055-4059
- [5] "Evaluating solid angles using contour integrals" von H.M.Haitjema Appl. Math. Modelling 1987, Vol.11 February p.69-71
- [6] Harald Schröer "Luminous flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001